

THE ANALYSIS OF CHARACTER EDUCATION IN INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

The basic problems of Indonesian Education is still not in accordance with the values of Pancasila indigo which if left unchecked could pose a threat to the existence of the nation. There are eighteen-character value that needs to be cultivated in a school environment that is implemented with intra-curricular and extracurricular activities dalma student life. Obstacles encountered in implementation include: the school has not been able to choose the values of characters in accordance with the vision, understanding of teachers about the concept of character education is still not complete, the teacher can not choose the character values corresponding to the subjects diampunya, teachers have not had sufficient competence to integrate value-niai character on subjects that diampunya, and teachers can not be an example of the values chosen character.

KEYWORDS

Pancasila, Character Education

1. BACKGROUND

Strengthening Character Education program (PPK), full-day school, and the number of days of school, become an issue of lively public discussion at the present time. The issues related to the discharge regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture number 23 in 2017. In the context of the number of school days, the regulation states that formal education schools to implement school five days a week, namely from Monday to Friday. This change habits and previous rules, which in many schools, implement learning day for six days each week. This provision resulted in extra hours of study at each school day from six hours to eight hours. Therefore, being familiar with the term called the school a full day or Ful-Day School (FDS).

In the context of strengthening character education, the regulation expressly (stated) aims to improve the character of the students. With the FDS system, the school-based learning activities to be long, and will reduce the time the child for the move were not relevant to the learning activity. Arguments academic paper said regulation also states that schools organize learning with FDS system, better character and superior achievement.

In another context, character education has also become a national program since the last decade. In the period of the previous administration, has also been done National Movement Character Education. Therefore, it can be said that the strengthening of Character Education (KDP) is a continuation of the National Character Education Movement which started in 2010. This is in line with one of the points Nawacita launched by President Joko Widodo through Mental Revolutionary National Movement (GNRM). On this basis, the Ministry of Education and Culture launched the Strengthening the Character Education (KDP) in stages starting in 2016¹

¹ Kemdikbud, 2017. Concepts and Guidelines for Strengthening the Character Education Elementary School and Junior High School.

In Indonesia, the nation's character education again become a hot topic since 2010. Development of the culture and character of the nation proclaimed by the Government to begin 'Declaration of Education Culture and National Character' as a national movement in January 2010. It reaffirmed the President's speech at the commemoration of National Education Day , May 2, 2010. Since then, the talk of character education at the national level. The declaration emergence allegedly due to the condition of our nation showing the behavior of anti-culture and anti character²

In the Nation Character Development National Policy states that form of activity in the nation's character education program the micro context, can be divided into four, namely: teaching and learning activities; activities of daily life in the educational unit; extracurricular activities; daily activities in the home and community. Considering the students as a group of idealist with all the advantages and potential, granting them national character education requires specific strategies. Birth of government policy related to the development of cultural education and the character of the nation, as the description above, in addition based on the mandate of the law and a lot of input from the community through various activities, also can not be separated from the idea of the need for efforts to overcome or at least mitigate the problems that happening in the community, especially those related aspects of the culture and character of the nation. Education is considered as an alternative preventive and means a new generation of builders of a better nation which is believed to reduce the problems associated with the culture and character of the nation. Curriculum as the heart of education, for development more emphasis on the strengthening of the values associated with cultural aspects and character of the nation.³

Through business that is developing, the government seems to expect the implementation of the nation's culture and character education can be more optimally, functional and effective in accordance with its intended purpose. Thus, an attempt to give birth and nurture individuals who are cultured and character that can be the strength of the nation, especially for the future, it would be able to be realized. This effort is in line with the spirit and ideals of the nation of Indonesia as summarized in the '45 Constitution and national educational goals.

Departing from the context, nature and spirit desired by the government through a policy of education development of culture and national character above, then the in-depth study of the policy needs to be done, in order to be understood and explored the various advantages and disadvantages as well as the implications for the community in general and the world special education. With understand the various aspects contained in the policy, then the next is expected to be generated options for improvement that can be taken into consideration for the government to improve or enhance the policy for the better. The following article analyzes the implementation of national character education has been implemented by the Government of Indonesia. In this paper the authors raised the title: Analysis of Character Education in Indonesia.

2. FORMULATION OF THE PROBLEM:

In this paper the authors limited the problem by providing the formulation of the problem how the implementation of character education in Indonesia?

3. DISCUSSION

In Indonesian Dictionary (2008) mentioned that the character is a psychological traits, morals/manners that distinguish one person with another person in the Nation Character Development Policy 2010-2025 (2010) stated that the character of the nation is the quality of the typical

² Marzuki. 2013. Revitalization Religious Education in Schools in the Nation Character Development in the Future. *Journal of Character Education*. 3 (1): 64-76.

³ Ministry of National Education Curriculum Research and Development Agency, Development of Culture and National Character Education: 2010. Guidelines for School p 1.

national collective behavior, both of which are reflected in the awareness, understanding, taste, intention, and behavior of the nation and the state as a result of a thought, though the heart, though the taste, and imagination, as well as the sports person or group of people. The character of the Indonesian nation will determine the collective behavior of the Indonesian nation typical, well reflected in the awareness, understanding, taste, intention, and behavior of nation and state of Indonesia based on Pancasila values, norms 1945, diversity under the principle of unity in diversity and Homeland commitment.

Personality is not a character. Everyone has a different personality. Personality is a thing that can be said to be permanent and is a gift of birth are difficult to change since it is a unique mark of each person while the characters can be built and, according to psychologists, there is some value of the basic character of human beings is love to God and His creature (nature with its contents), responsibility, honesty, respect and courtesy, compassion, caring, and cooperation, confident, creative, work hard, and never give up, justice and leadership; kind and humble, tolerance, love of peace, unity and love.

Indonesian national character building embodies the mandate of Pancasila and the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution is based on the character development of the growing national problem of the moment, such as disorientation and not dihayatinya Pancasila values; limitations of integrated policy tools in realizing the values of Pancasila; shifting the value of ethics in the life of the nation; waning awareness of the cultural values of the nation; the threat of disintegration; and the weakening of national independence.⁴At the National Policy on Development of National Character, mentioned that the character of the nation is the quality of collective behavior nationality typical well-reflected in the awareness, understanding, taste, intention, and behavior of the state and nation as a result of a thought, though the heart, though the taste, and imagination, as well as sports person or group of people. The character of the Indonesian nation will determine the collective behavior of the Indonesian nation typical well-reflected in the awareness, understanding, taste, intention, and behavior of nation and state of Indonesia based on Pancasila values, norms 1945, diversity under the principle of unity in diversity, and commitment to Homeland.

It is further mentioned that for the advancement of the Republic of Indonesia, needed a tough character, competitive, high morals, bertoleran, worked together, patriotic, dynamic, cultured, and oriented science and technology based on Pancasila and animated by faith and piety to God Almighty. The characters are based on the philosophy of Pancasila means that every aspect of the characters must be animated to the five principles of Pancasila fully and comprehensively include: 1) the nation's air Almighty God, 2) nation that upholds humanity just and civilized, 3) the nation that emphasizes unity and the unity of the nation, 4) a democratic nation and uphold the law and human rights, and 5) the nation that puts justice and prosperity. Legality, the characters have a legal education as follows:

Education is a conscious effort to develop learners' potential optimally. Conscious effort should not be removed from the environment of the learners are, especially on the cultural environment, because students live inseparable in their environment and act according to the rules of the culture. Education which is not based on the principles that will lead learners deprived of its cultural roots. When this happens, then they will not know the culture so well that he became a "foreigner" in a cultural environment. In addition to being a stranger is more worrying is that she be people who do not like the culture.

Culture, causing learners to grow and develop, at the start of the culture in the immediate neighborhood (RT, RW, village holder) evolved into the wider environment that is the nation's

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Parent Book Nation Character Development National Policy 2010-2025

national culture and universal culture embraced by mankind. If students become culturally alien from nearby then he is not familiar with the culture of the nation and do not recognize themselves as members of the nation's culture. The stronger the person has a basic consideration, the stronger the tendency to grow and develop into good citizens. Therefore, the basic rules governing the national education (UUD 1945 and the Education Law) already provide a solid foundation for developing the overall potential of oneself as a member of the community of nations.

1. Mandate of 1945

- a) Article 31, paragraph 3: "The Government shall manage and hasten a national education system, which enhances faith and piety and good character in the context of national life that is governed by law".
- b) Article 31, paragraph 5: "The government is advancing science and technology to uphold religious values and national unity for the progress of civilization and the welfare of mankind".

2. Mandate of the National Education System Law No. 20 of 2003

"National education serves to develop the ability and character development and civilization of the nation's dignity in the context of educating the nation aimed at developing students' potentials in order to become a man of faith and fear of God Almighty, noble, capable, creative, independent, and become citizens democratic and accountable".

3. Law No. 17 of 2007 on RPJPN 2005-2025
4. Law No. 20 of 2003 on National Education System
5. Presidential Decree No. 1 of 2010 on Accelerating the Implementation of National Development Priorities in 2010
6. Referral President in the Limited Cabinet Meeting of Public Welfare dated March 18, 2010
7. Referral President on National Working Meeting in Tampak Siring, Bali on 19-20 April 2010
8. Referral President at Peak National Education Day at the State Palace on May 11, 2010⁵

Ministry of Education has identified 18-characters value that needs to be imparted to the students who come from religion, Pancasila, Culture, and the National Education Goals. Eighteenth values are:

- 1) religious,
- 2) honest,
- 3) tolerance,
- 4) discipline,
- 5) hard work,
- 6) creative,
- 7) independent,
- 8) democratic,
- 9) curiosity,
- 10) spirit of nationality,
- 11) love of the homeland,
- 12) appreciate the achievements,
- 13) friends/ communicative,

⁵ Anas Salahudin, Character Education; Religious-Based Education and Culture of the Nation, (Bandung: Pustaka Setia CV, 2013). P. 41

- 14) love peace,
- 15) like to read,
- 16) environmental care,
- 17) Social care,
- 18) responsible.

Although there are 18 grades have been formulated forming the character of the nation, in every education unit can determine development priorities.⁶ Selection of these values stand of interests and conditions of each educational unit. This is done through the analysis of context, so that its implementation is possible there are different types of characters developed value. Implementation of character values that will be developed can be started from the values that are essential, simple, and easy to implement.

Character education is a lifelong education, as a process towards a perfect man. Therefore, education requires exemplary character and a touch start early adulthood. The period of the most sensitive and decisive is the education in the family which is the responsibility of parents. On the other hand mentioned that character education should be an integral part of education over the generations. Education is a humanitarian issue that should be approached from a human development itself.⁷

The first goal of character education is to facilitate the strengthening and development of certain values so manifest in the behavior of children, either when the school and after school process (after graduating from school). Strengthening and development has a meaning that education in the school environment is not just a dogmatization value to learners, but a process that brings learners to understand and reflect on how a value becomes important to be realized in people's daily behavior, including for children. Reinforcement is also directed at the habituation process is accompanied by logic and reflection on the process and impact of the habituation process conducted by the school both in the classroom and school. Strengthening also has the meaning of the relationship between behavior reinforcement through habituation habituation in schools with at home.

The second objective is to correct the behavior of the character education of students who did not correspond with the values developed by the school. This goal has a meaning that character education goal could be to straighten out various negative behaviors into positive children. The alignment process that is interpreted as a correction of the behavior of pedagogical understood as a process, not an imposition or pengkodisian that does not educate. Pedagogical process in correcting negative behavior directed at the child's mindset, and then coupled with exemplary school and home environment, and the process of habituation by level and jenjang school.

The third objective in character education school environment is establishing connections with family and community harmony in acting responsibility for character education together. This objective has the meaning that the process of character education in schools should be linked to the process of education in the family. If any character education in schools based solely on the interaction between learners and teachers in the classroom and school, then the achievement of the expected character will be very difficult to realize. Why? Because of the strengthening of behavior is something that is comprehensive (holistic) rather than a snippet of the span of time which is owned by the child. In every minute and second child's interactions with the environment will surely occur processes affect children's behavior.

⁶ Ministry of Education. 2011. Character Education Implementation Guide. Research and Development Agency and the Curriculum Center of Books. Jakarta.

⁷ Kartadinata, S. 2009. Looking Shape National Character Education. Papers. Faculty of Science Education. Indonesian education university. Bandung.

It is recognized education as the backbone in the strategy of national character formation. The development strategy of national character through education to do with education, learning, and facilitation. In the context of the macro, the implementation of character education covers all activities of planning, organizing, implementing, and quality control that involves all major units within the national education stakeholders. The role of education is very strategic because it is a strong national integration builder. Aside from being influenced political and economic factors, education is also influenced by social and cultural factors, especially in the aspect of integration and social resilience.

If it is associated with the scoring system used in the study of culture and national character based on the indicators as a measure carried out continuously while a student is in school, on the one hand requires all teachers to focus on every aspect of the student while in school, That is, in addition to demanding sensitivity and readiness of teachers also demanded professionalism of teachers as a true educator. In other words, the development of culture and national character education emphasizes focus on the teacher as a professional education in performing their duties, including in the assessment of learners. On the other hand, such an assessment of learning outcomes, it seems only limited tasks for teachers and students are in a school environment. This is not correlate with the activity of the students when they are out of school. If the implementation of the educational and cultural assessment and unsustainable character until the students are outside, so its implementation can not walk too effective.

When linked to the development of culture and national character education are pursued through the cultural program of the school, the goal of the assessment should make all elements of the school, such as principals, teachers and other employees as the party should also be evaluated. Evaluation is not only to those areas that do work or performance, but also in the area of personality development, as was done on students. For that, there needs assessment forms were addressed to the parties (non-students), like a form of self-assessment (self-assessment) associated with the nation's culture and character education. This self-assessment can also be used to assess student progress itself.

The implementation of the strategy of character education in schools can be done through a model of holistic education and integrative education. Holistic education model (holistic education) includes three (3) domain, the method of knowing the good, feeling the good and the good acting. Knowing the good form of the transfer of knowledge (cognitive) is good. After knowing the good must be grown feeling and loving the good, ie, how to feel and love of virtue into a drive that makes people always want to do something good that will do the behavior of a growing awareness of the virtues, for his love of virtue conduct it. Once accustomed to doing good, then acting the good form of concrete actions for the habit in their daily activities.

The educational model integrates done mengintegrasikan character values of the competencies of subjects. Implementation is through learning/ teaching, school culture development, and extra curricular activities. For example:

1. Teaching and Learning/ Learning and Teaching (KBM). To grow the value of the character's curiosity through observation, improve the skills to communicate effectively with the discussions and presentations, bound to develop critical thinking veloped with simple research activities
2. Culture School. To cultivate character melalau faith prayer beginning and end of the lesson, and/ or pray together, improve attitudes and behavior of deference/ respect to familiarize shake hands and say hello politely, to care for the environment by familiarizing character hygiene classes and taking out the trash in its place

3. Kegiatan Extracurricular: Scouts, Sports, Scientific, Art, PMR, etc. To develop the skills of cooperation and spirit of sportsmanship through playing sports, develop self-confidence through art shows, caring humanitarian blood donation PMR, social care by social services-relief.

Problems that occur at this time a policy is only to stop half way through the unfinished already appeared another policy, plus cabinet in the country of Indonesia is always changing every turn of the president. The lack of education focus in the running grooves create obscurity in education since every turn of the cabinet then also change the education policy. The changing of education model will change this model and makes clear the character of the young generation (not character). By the turn of the educational model that has been applied it has the reason that the development of the educational model. Supposedly with the development of a student will be more developed but instead more developed backwards.

Education is a public access, where education is the key answer to problems that occur in our country, but instead of education is a major project that could generate more money. Education is now the turn direction of the purpose and function of education that has been written in the Law on the National Education System 20 of 2003 Section 2 of Article 3. The concept of character education learning education instituted if want to succeed it must be garrisoned/ combine formal learning and boarding systems karen core point someone who was instrumental in character education is the Teacher, Student, Guardians of students and community leaders. Actually, a simple goal in education is to supervise the students good character in environmental education was or outside educational institutions.

Some alternatives that can be offered to make the material cultural education and character development of the nation for the better. Are as follows:

1. The need for an explanation of the nature of the nation's culture and character education needs to be analyzed more integrated. In addition, the meaning of culture and national character education needs to be defined more applicable in order to be well understood to be implemented in the field.
2. Integration courses in subjects demanding commitments should be agreed upon and addressed carefully. Education culture and national character are integrated in all subjects in the process of development should really be accommodated in school level education curriculum.
3. Need for closer scrutiny of the implementation of the policy by involving many parties, especially the input from academia (scientists) need to be taken into consideration, not just a political interest.

4. CONCLUSION

Bad behavior characters or no character can be seen in sekama with the increasingly widespread brawl between students, their promiscuity, and their socio-economic disparities and political society, environmental damage that occurred throughout the country, still injustice law, violence and unrest , and corruption is endemic and penetrated in all sectors of public life, anarchy, social conflict. Habituation to do good, habituation to behave with honesty, mutual help, tolerance, shy berrbuat cheated, embarrassed to be lazy, shame to let the dirty environment. Because the character is not formed in an instant, but should be trained in a serious, continuous and proportionate in order to achieve the ideal form of character.

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